

So you think you're a math person: Understanding cognitive dimensions of stereotypes in mathematics

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Research consistently documents a “math person” stereotype that positions white and male students as most mathematically able, and so reproduces gender and racial inequity in the field. Recent work suggests that this stereotype also includes how “math people” think, learn, and problem-solve, alongside how they look. This exploratory study combines survey and interview methods to examine if certain stereotyped cognitive attributes (such as a student’s preferred problem-solving style) influence students’ and teachers’ perceptions of other students as more or less mathematically able. Initial results support the hypothesis, with interview data also illustrating how the cognitive component interacts with broader stereotypes to shape students’ experiences and define them as belonging or not in math classrooms and careers.

Introduction and literature

If you study or teach mathematics it’s hard not to hear the phrase “math person,” whether in the classroom, the literature, or just day-to-day conversation (Devlin, 2000; Heller, 2016). Unsurprisingly, the “math person” label is not simply a throwaway one. It carries real meaning for how individuals view themselves and others as belonging – or not belonging – in mathematics classes and institutions.

Stereotypes are socially legitimized and reproduced beliefs that people in certain social groups have, or are more likely to have, certain characteristics (Steele, 2010). In the case of “math people,” the stereotype is a consequence of narratives that intertwine individuals’ *mathematical* identity (their sense of competency and belonging in mathematics) with other social group identities such as race and gender (McGee, 2015; Steele, 2010). These narratives become embedded in institutions as well as individuals, legitimizing practices that position white and male students as more mathematically able than female, Black, and/or Brown students (Kim et al., 2018).

From middle school to university in the United States, Black and female students are less likely than their white male peers to be placed in and take high-level math courses, independent of their academic record (Faulkner et al., 2014; Francis et al., 2019; Treisman, 1992). Women, and especially women of color, consistently experience feelings of “not fitting” in STEM classrooms unless they conform to a narrow and constricting idea of what women in mathematics “are like” (Kim et al., 2018). They are also more likely to experience

Please cite as: Ruley, G. (2021). So you think you're a math person: Understanding cognitive dimensions of stereotypes in mathematics. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 878–888). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457238>

social math identity dissonance, where individuals do not think they are “math people” even though they believe others perceive them this way (Heller, 2016). The “math person” stereotype and the narratives behind it also attack students’ own sense of mathematical competence, and can depress their academic performance (Spencer et al., 2016; Steele, 2010).

These effects can occur even in situations where there is equal gender and/or racial representation (Kim et al., 2018). In short, pervasive stereotypes of white male mathematical superiority create both structural and personal barriers that traditionally-excluded students in math classrooms must contend with. While students can and do fight back, building communities and “robust” mathematical identities that support them in defying the stereotype, they are overall less likely to develop the positive mathematical identity necessary for any student’s persistence in the field (Boaler, 2002; Heller, 2016; McGee, 2015; McGee & Martin, 2011)

While the racial and gender components of the stereotype are well documented, there may also a *cognitive* component that “math people” *think* in certain ways as well as *look* certain ways. Much of the prior cited work, as well as many general-audience pieces about mathematics in society, note the association of “math people” with words like “logical,” “objective,” or “rational” (Burton, 1999; Devlin, 2000; Lakatos, 1976). Additionally, recent work shows that presentations of how one must think and problem-solve in mathematics can directly lead to students feeling inclusion or exclusion.

In a study of AP Calculus courses in California, Boaler and Greeno (2000) found that the methods of thinking and problem-solving presented by math teachers affected students’ feelings of belonging in mathematics. In classrooms where math was a “closed” field where single, right answers were found through inflexible methods, students who enjoyed thinking more critically, or debating multiple answers, felt out of place and reported that mathematics “wasn’t right for them” (Boaler & Greeno, 2000). On the other hand, “open” classrooms that encouraged multiple methods of inquiry supported a greater diversity of students to grow positive mathematical identities. The fact that students experienced inclusion or exclusion based on a “cognitive” identity, and the common association of “math people” with “logical” or “objective” ways of thinking, suggests the possibility that the “math person” stereotype may also be a stereotype about how mathematicians *think* – as well as how they look.

This leads to the following research questions exploring the potential existence of a cognitive component of the “math person” stereotype:

1. Do students and teachers evaluate the likelihood of other students’ interest and success in math differently, based on characteristics signaling different forms of cognitive identity?
2. Do students experience math education differently based on their cognitive identities?

If there is a cognitive component to the “math person” stereotype, we would expect school experiences to reflect this in some way. Students who identify more with the stereotypical way of thinking would be more likely to be perceived as “math people,” while

students *not* so identifying would be less likely to receive the label. If there isn't a cognitive component to the stereotype, then a student's preferred way of thinking would not affect their internal or external perception as a "math person."

The first step in studying possible cognitive components of the "math person" stereotype is to operationalize those components. Drawing on the literature, I propose the following list of possible cognitive stereotype components. Math people:

1. think logically (vs. intuitively) (Burton, 1999; Devlin, 2000),
2. prefer certainty and problems with definitive answers (vs. uncertainty and problems with multiple competing answers) (Boaler & Greeno, 2000; Lakatos, 1976),
3. prefer to be told unquestionable facts (vs. debating or critiquing knowledge) (Boaler, 2002).

I hypothesize that the first component of each of these pairs forms a stereotype of how "math people" think. That is, they define a "way of thinking" that is socially perceived as being necessary or important to enjoying and succeeding in mathematics, while the opposite "way of thinking" is not useful for doing math or is even an active hindrance.

If the stereotypical "way of thinking" were somehow more necessary for doing mathematics than other ways of thinking, then it wouldn't be stereotypical – it would just be generally necessary for doing math. However, it cannot be over-emphasized that *none* of the hypothesized stereotyped characteristics *actually are* more necessary to doing mathematics than their opposites. While mathematical inquiry frequently is logical, and math research questions frequently have definitive answers, mathematics throughout history has also relied on intuition, debate, and intense questioning of assumptions. Researchers, math educators, and mathematicians all agree on this point: mathematics is as much of a contested, living, uncertain field as any other, and intuition, uncertainty, and debate characterize mathematical work just as much as logic, certainty and "truth" (see, e.g., Klein, 1982; Burton, 1999; and Lakatos, 1976).

Methods

This study employs mixed methods to shed as much light as possible on the potential existence of a "way of thinking" stereotype. A vignette-type survey of students at Swarthmore College and teachers in the Philadelphia area was used to assess if the presence or absence of the stereotyped way of thinking affected a student's external perception as a "math person." The survey was followed by interviews with volunteers from both populations to explore in more detail where the "math person" stereotype is encountered and how it impacts educational experiences.

The survey consisted of four sections: an introduction obtaining informed consent and asking if the participant was a teacher or student; a vignette presenting a hypothetical student profile, followed by questions about that student; questions about respondent attitude towards and experience in mathematics; and lastly demographic questions. Students were recruited using social media posts, and messages through departmental mailing lists.

Teachers who had graduated from Swarthmore College or who had hosted Swarthmore students in their classrooms for fieldwork were contacted through Swarthmore's alumni network and asked to share the survey with their own contacts. Through the college Department of Educational Studies, the survey was also distributed to teacher groups and organizations in the Philadelphia area.

The vignette was the central analytic tool of the survey. The vignette described a hypothetical student and varied three aspects of the student's identity: their gender, their interests and habits, and their "way of thinking." Each aspect had two poles: one hypothesized to be a part of the "math person" stereotype, the other not. Vignette names were chosen from the 20 most common names for both White and Black high-school-aged children in the U.S., though this does not prevent the respondent from making assumptions about the student's racial identity (U.S. Social Security Administration, 2019).

Each respondent read a vignette version that randomized the factors presented (stereotypical/not stereotypical for each). They were not told that the project was specifically studying stereotypes in math. They were next asked to predict the student's interest and success in five school subjects (math, natural science, foreign language, social studies, and English) on a five-point Likert-type scale. Response patterns to the post-vignette questions would then ideally capture the salience of each factor in shaping perceptions of the student. Although imperfect, by asking for reactions to a concrete situation the vignette provided a more robust construct than directly asking respondents about their beliefs (Bryman, 2004). The factors, with text, are reproduced in Table 1.

Gender functioned as a control variable. Given significant evidence that "math people" are stereotyped as male, if no differences in hypothetical student perception were observed based on gender, the survey may not be capturing authentic reactions. *Way of Thinking* was the key variable, as it operationalized the cognitive components hypothesized to be a part of the "math person" stereotype. *Personality* separated a student's specific "way of thinking" from any associations the survey-taker might have between ways of thinking and a student's more general personality and interests.

The survey was built using Qualtrics XM and distributed electronically. Question order was randomized when applicable. Written consent for the use and sharing of the data was collected at the beginning of the survey, and the survey would not allow completion unless consent was given. The survey opened on December 2nd, 2018 and closed on February 6th, 2019. Data was analyzed using the open-source statistical computing tool R.

The final question of the survey asked if the respondent was willing to participate in an interview. Student interview participants were selected semi-randomly to vary class year and subjects studied. To maximize data relevance, teacher interview participants primarily taught mathematics and were varied across grades taught. In total five students and three teachers were interviewed. Questions focused on participants' own conception of the "math person" stereotype, if the stereotype was justified, and their experiences of encountering the stereotype in school and work.

Factor	Hypothesized Stereotyped pole	Hypothesized Non-stereotyped pole
Gender	Male	Female
Personality ("Academic" or "Creative")	"Academic" personality "[Student] is on the quiz bowl team and goes to debate club when [she/he] has time. [Her/his] room is usually tidy and she/he has separate notebooks for each class."	"Creative" personality "[Student] sings in the school choir and performs with the poetry club when [she/he] has time. [Her/his] room is usually messy and she/he keeps all her/his school notes in one large binder."
Way of Thinking ("Objective" or "Subjective")	"Objective" way "[Student] has strong opinions and defends them with reasoned arguments. [He/she] enjoys finding right and wrong answers to questions, and [he/she] believes that objectively correct answers exist in most cases. [She/he] prefers classes where the teacher spends most of the period lecturing, and in class [she/he] asks challenging questions that build on the information being presented."	"Subjective" way "[Student] has strong opinions and defends them with references to [her/his] personal experience. [He/she] enjoys finding multiple answers to the same question, and [she/he] believes that objectively correct answers don't exist in most cases. [He/she] prefers classes where the teacher spends most of the period on independent projects, and in class [she/he] asks challenging questions that critique the information being presented."

Table 1: Stereotype factors selected for analysis, with vignette text.

Interviews were semi-structured and lasted approximately one hour each. Written and verbal consent for the recording of the interview, and the use and analysis of the transcripts, were collected at the beginning of each interview. The interviews were transcribed by hand and Atlas.ti was used for coding.

Results

One hundred and thirty Swarthmore students and eighty-two teachers responded to the survey. A majority of respondents identified as women (73%) and a majority identified as white (60%). Students were more racially diverse than teachers, and the racial distribution of students was generally representative of the student body at Swarthmore College (Swarthmore College, 2018). Students spanned class years evenly, but 78% of majors were in social or natural science. Most students and teachers were upper-middle or upper class. English literature, mathematics, and social studies were the most common primary subjects for teachers. Three-fifths of teachers were not alumni of Swarthmore College. On average students were slightly less likely to identify as math people than teachers, and slightly less likely to enjoy doing math.

Teacher and student responses to the vignette battery varied based on the vignette presented. Overall, the more that the vignette student possessed a hypothesized stereotyped identity, the more that student was perceived as likely to be interested in and successful in mathematics (Figure 1). Students had higher variation in responses and appeared to be more sensitive to vignette factors than teachers, while for both groups the hypothetical vignette student's perceived interest in math was more affected by vignette factors than perceived success (Figure 1).

Linear models were constructed to examine which of the vignette factors had the greatest effect independent of the other two. The salience of "Way of Thinking" was maintained in the models for both teachers and students (Figure 2; Figure 3). Few other recorded variables had a visible effect on predicted interest or success for either group; the only ones to have a significant effect were teachers' enjoyment of doing math, and teacher respondent gender (Figure 3).

The survey data supports the hypothesis that the "math person" stereotype contains a cognitive component. The more stereotypical traits the hypothetical student had (being male, being academic, or having an objective way of thinking), the more they were judged to be interested in *and* to be successful in mathematics (Figure 1). The apparent effect of vignette

Figure 1: Mean predicted Interest and Success for the hypothetical vignette student, by vignette factor (n = 212).

Key: M/F = male/female, A/C = academic/creative, O/S = objective/subjective.

Figure 2: Linear model slope estimates using an ordinary least-squares method for the influence of seven ordinal factors on student-predicted hypothetical student interest in mathematics (n = 130).

factors on respondent answers is corroborated by the linear models, which show “Way of Thinking” (labeled in the figure as “Approach to Knowledge”) to be the factor associated with the greatest change in student and teacher perceptions, followed in salience by “Personality,” then “Gender” (Figure 2; Figure 3). While the latter two factors have a substantive effect on student perceptions, neither influences teacher perceptions.

This suggests that the teachers in the survey pool are more resistant to stereotypes around mathematics, possibly due to their greater experience with math as compared to the students. Or perhaps they are just careful in their responses. Either way direct observation would be necessary to validate this apparent pattern of teachers’ less-stereotypical perception of students.

Overall, we conclude that for this survey sample, the “way of thinking” factor appears to have robust effects on a student’s external perception as interested and likely to succeed in mathematics. However, the non-random survey sample and the relative inapplicability of linear models to this data make stronger conclusions impossible.

Data from the interviews corroborate these findings, but also describe a “math person” stereotype that is richer and more subtle than the tested survey factors. The wealth of insight provided by the interviews into the stereotype was much greater than can be analyzed in this paper; I will thus focus on the three most relevant themes.

Firstly, “way of thinking” was described by students as being either a meaningful factor in their experience, or as a part of the “math person” stereotype. Words like “ordered” and “logical” were used to describe this way of thinking. These descriptions corroborate the survey, and offer evidence that students compare themselves (or are compared) to this way of thinking as they build their mathematical identity.

Student 4: I, it really just seems like a way of thinking...the words that come to mind are *logical*, um, like an ordered way of thinking...

Student 5: I feel like the question that I was always asked...were like, ‘if you like xyz then you should pursue this career,’ and I always remember one of the questions being ‘if you like knowing that there are concrete answers to questions, you should go into math or science.’

Figure 3: Linear Model Slope estimates using an ordinary least-squares method for the influence of eight ordinal factors on teacher-predicted hypothetical student interest in mathematics ($n = 82$).

Secondly, both students and teachers mentioned *other* factors when describing “math people,” alongside way of thinking, race, and gender. These included an ability to calculate quickly and a strong interest in math to the exclusion of other pursuits.

Student 2: I mean, working within the framework of stereotypical math people, I think it's generally people who are numerically inclined, would rather think about things in terms of numbers than in terms of words, and people who usually do math quickly, um, and who do it accurately, like, the first time around...

Student 5: I know the things that immediately come to mind are really not true, like I always imagine like a math person, in quotes to be like, if I'm honest visualizing a white guy sitting like at a desk with frazzled hair, and has been working on a single problem for like days, like generally introverted I would say, and not a great communicator with other people (laughs)...

As seen in the second quote, interviewees were frequently aware that the factors they were describing were stereotypical, and they did not necessarily believe that these stereotypes were accurate portrayals of mathematics or mathematicians. These findings also give insight into how the stereotype is reproduced in practice: for example, an ability to calculate quickly will aid performance on typical school assessments, and so reinforce the student's identification as a “math person.” In fact, both students and teachers were often aware of this chain of events, and directly connected factors of the “math person” stereotype to the math abilities that are valued and privileged by typical U.S. mathematics curricula.

Student 4: I self-identify as creative, um, which I think, had I maybe been in a different sort of math setting, would have been more valued, um, but for the majority of math classes I took it was really just memorization and problem solving, and never proofs or the cooler kind of jumping around stuff, yeah...

Student 3: I think there's people who have like test anxiety and stuff, so they do bad in math classes, um, and people who can't do math quickly, and so do we consider them to be bad at math?...But if you think about high-level mathematics, I mean, you're sitting with a problem for a long time and figuring it out doesn't make you any less good. So I don't know....but I think people will never go and become higher mathematicians being told they're whole life that they're bad at math because they're slow...

Lastly, perhaps the most striking finding was that all but one participant (a teacher) did not identify as a math person. This included two other math teachers and two students completing STEM majors. However, many *had* identified as “math people” in the past, before other experiences caused them to change their identification.

Student 4: I think in seventh grade when I got to go into higher math...I was just having fun, I would stay after school and do math, I was like ‘Yeah, I guess I am a math person,’ then I got into the science-y high school...I actually do remember taking a hit to my confidence when I only got in to the second lowest [track], I was like ‘Oh, I guess I'm not that good at math...

The participants' math histories suggest that on top of the direct factors comprising the "math person" stereotype, there is also an "infallibility" component: after either a) experiences of difficulty or failure in mathematics, or b) comparison to students more capable in/more interested in mathematics than themselves, students drop their "math person" identity. One cannot be a math person if one struggles in math.

Discussion

Although not complete, our data begins to paint a better picture of the "math person" stereotype. Survey data supports the hypothesis that "math people" are stereotyped as orderly, logical people with an "objective" way of thinking (Figure 1). They calculate quickly, are more rational than creative, and don't appear to struggle to do math. Interviews add that the stereotype is reproduced in the U.S. both by discourse around who likes math and why, and by norms of teaching and assessment that link quick calculation and infallibility to school success. Being a "math person" is, however, a fickle belonging, as failure or struggle can quickly lead to losing the label. In short, the cognitive stereotype carries social power that sorts students into and out of mathematics through feelings of exclusion and not being "good enough."

The limitations of a one-year project constrained the design of this study, including a non-representative survey sample, no opportunity to use fieldwork or trial surveys to inform the final survey design, and time for only eight interviews. While the findings are robust given the available data, they are not safely generalizable and require validation with a better-tested survey battery and larger dataset. I also rely on accurate self-reporting by participants, and so would benefit from confirmation through more direct methods (Jerolmack & Khan, 2014). Finally, the survey sample size required that the "Gender" variable be a strict binary, and that gender and race could not both be included as variables alongside "Personality" and "Way of Thinking." Given that the math person stereotype is deeply racialized, any future work must study the interactions of the cognitive factors with a students' racial identity as well.

Should these results be reproducible, they have implications for both further research and educational practice. The individual effects of the "way of thinking" component on student self-perception described in interviews mirror prior findings on racial and gender stereotypes, as the component affects students' mathematical identities and their perception of their belonging in mathematics (Boaler, 2002; McGee, 2015). Thus a "way of thinking" stereotype can theoretically be combated using interventions already proven to help address other stereotypes (e.g., Steele, 2010). Stereotypes thrive when they are unarticulated and unchallenged, meaning that the first step to dismantling the stereotype is to articulate it and call it out in all its forms.

But stereotypes are only symptoms of larger social narratives around belonging and ability. They can also operate unconsciously, a fact echoed by how interviewed students largely rejected the stereotype, but on the survey student respondents upheld it over all factors (Spencer et al., 2016). Creating math classrooms that support all students requires

tackling those larger structures. We must ask how “way of thinking” is used in constructing legitimate belonging in mathematics, and explore in more detail how this stereotype is communicated – and enforced – to students. Given the history of concepts like “ability” being weaponized to uphold white and male superiority, we should also explore how the cognitive stereotype is used to support the construction of Black and female students as “less able” in mathematical spaces and so legitimize their exclusion, even in the absence of explicit racism and misogyny. Ideas like the cognitive stereotype may be providing a convenient colorblind excuse for patterns like those observed by Faulkner et al. (2014) and Francis et al. (2019).

Lastly, since the cognitive stereotype affects students' persistence in math, the stereotype goes beyond student experience to actively shape the composition of larger mathematical communities. Building on work by researchers such as Boaler (2002) and Lakatos (1976), future work can explore how the “way of thinking” component of the stereotype affects mathematical communities, and especially ask if the stereotype has consequences for how legitimate mathematical knowledge is produced – and what knowledges and skills are considered “mathematical” in the first place.

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